

Ontologies in Variation

Extended abstract of the COSIT 2024 doctoral mentorship program

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A knowledge graph, coupled with an associated ontology, can be used to capture explicit semantic relations between entities of interest. It does so using triples of the form (*subject*, *relation*, *object*), where the object can be an entity or data related to the subject. While knowledge graphs excel at capturing concrete relations, they are not inherently well-suited to dealing with uncertainty. For example, while we generally accept a statement like (dock, overlaps, waterbody) as true, in reality it is true most but not all of the time; e.g., it may not be true near some low tides or during droughts.

Uncertainty can arise in just about any situation and in many different ways. There are generic statements that are not always true like (dock, overlaps, waterbody). Sometimes there are fuzzy quantifiers like “very” or “more”; e.g., distinguishing between docks that are short, long, and very long. There can be substantial geospatial variation within and across regions, such as with chemical contamination of the environment.

Considerable effort has been expended developing methods to work with uncertainty in knowledge graphs. The predominant methods have used subjective probabilities within a Bayesian framework. Little attention has been given to empirical, or frequentist, approaches. I propose characterizing and using empirical measures of variation in data in knowledge graphs as an alternative to existing approaches. Instead of trying to model uncertainty (what we do not know or do not know for certain), or working with probability (and the associated “degrees of belief”), I will focus on empiricism, working with what we do know.

Languages for defining the structure of a knowledge graph (ontology), such as the Web Ontology Language (OWL), are not well-suited to representing empirical statistics about data variation. Therefore, I propose an extension of OWL that allows for the storage and manipulation of empirical statistical information for data within a knowledge graph. I have identified three primary research questions at this time. They are: can we extend OWL to incorporate and process empirical statistical information, can we reason effectively and efficiently with data using such an OWL extension, and can we automatically update the statistics when the underlying data changes?

The first task will be creating a set of competency questions to serve as examples of the types of questions users might like to ask a knowledge graph created using the proposed OWL extension. Requirements for the extension will be derived from this set of competency questions. OWL will be extended with new semantic concepts and relations to allow for storage of and reasoning about variation. Such an extension must balance functionality, complexity, and decidability. It will be used to construct a knowledge graph and that knowledge graph will be evaluated using the original competency questions.

I am hopeful the research will have the following results: the proposed OWL extension along with examples of its use, automatic incorporation of data changes in subsequent query results, and correct functionality for different types of data (e.g., qualitative vs. quantitative). Further, it should be relatively simple to use the language extension with existing OWL-based knowledge graphs (that is, it will not be necessary to rebuild existing graphs from scratch).

The goal is the ability to create self-contained knowledge graphs that include clear definitions, human-comprehensible semantics, data, and empirical statistics describing the

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data. Ideally, these knowledge graphs will be able to incorporate statistical assertions as well as aggregate statistics from data.